

VOLEYBOL O'YINIDA SAKROVCHANLIK SIFATINING AHAMIYATI

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***Annotatsiya.** Bu maqolada umum ta'lim va o'rta maxsus ta'lim va oliy o'quv yurti talabalarini voleybol mashg'lulotida jismoniy tayorgarligini oshirish usullari va jismoniy sifatlarni rivojlantirish uchun maxsus mashqlardan foydalanish, rivojlantirish usullari haqida nazariy ma'lumot berilgan. Jismoniy tayorgarlik va xususan sportchilarni tayyorlashda, harakat sifatlarini (tezkorlik, kuch, chidamkorlik, chaqqonlik, egiluvchanlik) bir-biriga bog'lab shakllantirish rivojlantirishning nazariy-pedagogik asoslarini yoritib berilgan.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** Jismoniy madaniyat, jismoniy sifatlar, sakrovchanlik, voleybol elementlarini rivojlantirish, maxsus mashqlar.*

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE QUALITY OF THE BALL IN THE GAME OF VOLLEYBALL.

***Abstract.** This article provides theoretical information about the methods of improving the physical fitness of general education and secondary special education and higher education students in volleyball training, and the use and development of special exercises for the development of physical qualities. The theoretical-pedagogical foundations of the development of movement qualities (speed, strength, endurance, agility, flexibility) in connection with physical training, especially in the training of athletes, have been explained.*

***Key words:** Physical culture, physical qualities, agility, development of volleyball elements, special exercises.*

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ КАЧЕСТВА МЯЧА В ИГРЕ В ВОЛЕЙБОЛ.

***Аннотация.** В статье представлены теоретические сведения о методах повышения физической подготовленности учащихся общеобразовательных и средних специальных учебных заведений и высших учебных заведений при тренировках по волейболу, а также использованию и разработке специальных упражнений для развития физических качеств. Изложены теоретико-педагогические основы развития двигательных качеств (скорости, силы, выносливости, ловкости, гибкости) в связи с физической подготовкой, особенно в подготовке спортсменов.*

***Ключевые слова:** Физическая культура, физические качества, ловкость, развитие элементов волейбола, специальные упражнения.*

Sakrovchanlik - bu vertikal yoki gorizontall masofani yengib o'tish uchun yuqori darajada mushak va irodaviy kuchlanishli qobiliyatdir. Voleybolchilar uchun asosiy jismoniy sifatlardan biri sakrovchanlikdir. Sakrovchanlik tezkor kuchlilik sifatlariga mansub bo'lib oyoq mushaklarining qisqa muddat ichida kuchli qisqarish bilan ifodalanadi. Aynan shu sifatni yuksak darajada bo'lishi nisbatan past bo'yi o'yinchilarni baland bo'yi o'yinchilar bilan raqobatini va asosiy o'yin malakalarini (zarba va to'siq qo'yish samarali ijro etilishini ta'minlaydi. (V.D. Kovalov 1980). Sakrovchanlikni rivojlantirish uchun esa qulay davr bu 10-12 yoshdir. Bu davrda

yosh voleybolchilarda joydan turib balandga sakrash 12,5 sm gacha ortishi kuzatiladi. (Ye.V.Fomin 1986).

Sakrovchanlik sifatining turlari ko'p. Masalan, ikki oyoq bilan debsinib yugurib kelib yoki joydan turib vertikal sakrash bir oyoq bilan debsinib vertikal yoki uzunlikka sakrash, ikki oyoq bilan debsinib uzunlikka sakrash va xokazo. Har bir sakrash turining o'ziga xos maqsadi va maqsadga mos ijro etish tartibi (texnikasi) bo'ladi. Voleybol, basketbol, futbol va boshqa sport o'yinlari bilan shug'ullanuvchi sportchilarning sakrovchanligi bir-biridan farq qiladi.

Ta'kidlash lozimki, hatto bir sport o'yinida, masalan voleybolda- zarba yoki to'siq qo'yish, to'p kiritish yoki uzatish uchun ijro etiladigan sakrashlar mohiyati jihatidan bir-biriga sira o'xshamaydi. (Golomazov V.A., Kovalev V.D., Melnikov A.Gyu 1976). Boz ustiga yana shuni eslatish o'rinliki, faqat bir o'yin malakasi – zarba berish, turiga qarab (qisqa yoki baland to'pdan zarba berish) sakrash xususiyati umuman boshqacha bo'ladi. Binobarin, sakrovchanlik yoki sakrash chidamkorligi degan tushuncha ko'p qamrovli mazmun, mohiyat xususiyat va ma'noni anglatadi. Demak, bu sifatlarni rivojlantirish haqida gap berganda muayyan sakrash turi va uni o'ziga munosib mashqlariga alohida e'tibor berilishiga muhim masaladir.

So'nggi yillarda voleybol musobaqasi qoidalarining tubdan o'zgarish o'yin faoliyati va o'yin malakalarining ijro etilishiga batamom yangicha tus berib yuborgan. Hozirgi kunda deyarli barcha o'yin malakalari aksariyat vaziyatlarda «havoda» ya'ni sakrab ijro etiladi (zarba, to'siq qo'yish, to'p kiritish, uzatish, to'pni qabul qilish, yiqilib qabul qilish). Ushbu qolatni yuzaga kelishi voleybol amaliyotida sakrovchanlik va sakrash chidamkorligi sifatlariga e'tibor qaratishni nafaqat kuchaytiriyapti, balki bu sifatlarni jadal rivojlantirishga qaratilgan yangi ilmiy texnologiyalar yaratishni taqozo etmoqda. Shuning uchun, ko'p yillik sport tayyorgarligi jarayonida malakali voleybolchilarni tayyorlash samarasi sakrovchanlik va sakrash chidamkorligi sifatlarini har tomonlama mukammal tarbiyalash ustivorligiga bevosita bog'liq bo'lib boryapti.

Shunday ekan, yuqori malakali voleybolchilarni tayyorlash va ular sport mahoratini yuksak darajaga olib chiqish dastlabki o'rgatish jarayoni samaradorligiga to'g'ridan-to'g'ri bog'liqdir. Yu.D. Jeleznyak (1991) ni fikricha voleybolga ixtisoslashgan mashg'ulotlar bilan ilk bor shug'ullanishni 10-12 yoshdan boshlab maqsadga muvofiqdir. U o'zining tadqiqotlarida aynan shu yoshda bolalarni jismoniy va texnik tayyorgarligini jadal o'stirish imkoniyatlarini ochib berdi.

Isbot qilinganki dastlabki tayyorgarlik bosqichida yosh voleybolchilarning kelajakdagi istedodini aniqlashga yordam beridagan test mashqlarini tanlay bilib va qo'llash katta ahamiyatga ega. E.A. Sergeev bunday mashqlar qatoriga birinchi navbatda sakrovchanlik va chaqqonlikni baholovchi mashqlarni kiritish muhimligini ta'kidlaydi. Tayyorgarlikning keyingi bosqichlarida asosiy jismoniy sifatlarni, shu jumladan maxsus sifatlarni baholash imkoniyatini beruvchi test mashqlari tarkibini oshirish tavsiya etiladi. Albatta, sakrovchanlik va sakrash chidamkorligini rivojlantirish tayyorgarlikning qaysi bosqichida amalga oshirilishidan qat'iy nazar bu masala umumiy va maxsus jismoniy tayyorgarlik jarayonini qanday darajada rejalashtirilishiga bog'liq.

Shuning uchun ushbu jarayonning malakali voleybolchilarni tayyorlashdagi ahamiyati, qolaversa asosiy o'yin malakalarini (zarba berish, to'siq qo'yish) ijro etish samrasi, sakrovchanlik va sakrash chidamkorligiga to'g'ridan-to'g'ri bog'liqligi haqidagi ma'lumotlar taxlili aloxida ahamiyatga egadir.

Maxsus jismoniy tayyorgarlik (MJT) sport faoliyatidagi dolzarb muammolardan biridir va barcha sport turlarida yuksak sport natijalariga erishish uchun muhim ahamiyatga ega (V.V. Kuznesov. 1975, V.B. Sorvalov. 1979, Folin Ye.V. 1985, Z.K. Auremeus Kazis 1989, Chan Suan Dong 1987). Shuning uchun maxsus jismoniy sifatlarni (MJS) rivojlantirish sportchilarni musobaqa oldi tayyorgarligining asosiy yo'nalishlaridan biri bo'lib turibdi (S.S. Kryuchek 1981).

«Voleybolchilar trenirovkasining muvaffaqiyati, o'yinchilar MJSlarining rivojlanish darajasini aniq va to'g'ri nazorat qilishiga bog'liqdir. Pedagogik nazorat alohida MJS ni o'zgarish darajasi dinamikasini (sur'atini) aniqlash imkoniyatini beradi. Buni asosida MJT ni samarali boshqarishni yangi yo'llarini belgilash mumkin» (Ye.V. Fomin 1981). Negaki «tayyorgarlik tuzilishni oqilona tashkil etishni zamonaviy yo'llaridan biri, qisqa vaqt ichida sport formasini rivojlantirishni ko'p qirrali modelini tuzishdir». (V.I. Maksimova, V.A. Nikulichev 1983).

Jismoniy tayyorgarlikni pedagogik nazorat turlarini o'rganish; A.V. Belyaev 1978, Ch.I. Bondarevskiy 1983, M.A. Godik 1977, 1981, V.M. Zatsiorskiy 1982, Yu.A. Jendebin 1982, V.V. Solovev 1980, Ye.V. Fomin 1981 va boshqalarni ishlarida tez-tez uchraydi, ma'lum rivashdagi MJTni PN ning aniq belgilangan savollariga javob bera oladi.

Maktab yoshidagi bolalarning jismoniy tayyorgarligi hamda jismoniy tarbiya va sportga bo'lgan ehtiyojini oshirish uchun maktab jismoniy tarbiya shakli, vosita va uslubiyatini takomillashtirish zaruriyatini tug'diradi. (V.Zatsiorskiy).

Hozirgi jahon sportidagi ko'rsatkichlarning jadal ravishda yangilanib borayotganligi, yosh sportchilarni tayyorlashning yangi, yanada samarali vositalarini, uslublarini va shakllarini izlashni taqozo etadi (V.P. Platonov 1997, L.P. Matveev 1989, F.A. Kerimov 2001).

Ko'pgina tadqiqotlar (Kao Van Txe 1971, Yu.D. Jeleznyak 1973, A.V. Belyaev 1975, Ye.V. Fomin 1980, R.S. Nosimov 1990 va boshqalar) shuni ko'rsatadiki, voleybolchilarning sport mahoratini yuksalishi aksariyat xollarda tezkor-kuchlilik sifati bo'yicha belgilanadi. Ushbu sifatni rivojlantirish foleybolchilarni tayyorlashning muhim vazifalaridan biridir. (Jeleznyak Yu.D. 1978, Fomin Ye.V. 1979, Belyaev A.V. 1983, Noraliev M.A. 1987, Garipov A.T. 1990 va boshqalar).

Yuqorida qayd etilgan ma'lumotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, yosh voleybolchilarni maxsus jismoniy tayyorgarligini oshirish ularning texnik malakalarini shakllanishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Demak, yuqori malakali voleybolchilar tayyorlashda maxsus jismoniy sifatlarning ularning asosiy o'yin malakalarini takomillashtirishda muhim o'rinni egallaydi.

Voleybol nazariyasi va amaliyoti soxasi doirasidagi ko'pgina mutaxassislar fikricha (Kao Van Txe 1971, Misinish I.A. 1973, Kondak N.K. 1985, Kinku G.K. 1986, Jan Xak 1978). «sakrovchanlik» va sakrash tayyorgarligi voleybolchilarning o'yin davomida ijro etiladigan texnik malakalar samarasini belgilab beradi. Har bir o'yinda ishtirok etuvchi jamoa o'yinchilarning sport maxorati, jismoniy tayyorgarligi va o'yin partiyalarining davom etishiga qarab texnik malakalar hajmi va samaradorligi turlicha bo'lishi o'z-o'zidan ma'lum.

Yuqorida qayd etilganidek o'yin davomida sakrash sifatini nafaqat soni, balki uni qanday balandlikda ijro etilayotganligi ham katta ahamiyatga egadir. Shuning uchun bu sifatni dastlabki o'rgatish bosqichidan boshlab samarali mashqlar asosida shakllantirish zarur. Sakrovchanlik va sakrash chidamkorligini oshirishda nafaqat maxsus mashqlar, balki turli moslama trenajorlardan ham foydalanish yaxshi natija beradi.

Masalan; sakrash tumbasi sakrovchanlikni va sakrash chidamkorligini rivojlantiradi.

Tumba bo'limlaridan iborat bo'lib, har xil balandlikka qo'yish mumkin. Asosan sakrovchanlikni oshirishda bajariladigan mashqlar quyidagilardan iborat. Bir oyoqda va ikki oyoqda doksini sakrash, sakrab o'tish, yuqoriga sakrash va hujumchi zarbasini bajarishdagi sakrashlar kiradi. Sakrash espanderida mashq bajarish sakrovchanlikni rivojlantiradi. Bunda belgi va polga amortizator boylanadi va osilib turgan to'pga qo'lni tekkizish uchun sakraladi.

Mashqlarni nazorat qilishda shug'ullanuvchilarni jixozlardan to'g'ri foydalanishi va mashqlarni to'g'ri va aniq bajarilishiga e'tibor berish kerak.

Yuqorida keltirilgan mashqlarni bir maromda bajarish yosh voleybolchilarda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Yana shuni aytib o'tish joizki sportchi sakrash quvvatini va epcillik xarakterini aniq bir mo'ljalga olgan holda to'pga o'sha kuch-quvvatini sarflamog'i kerak. Voleybolchi o'z zonasiga javob bergan holda xujum zarbasini yoki to'pni uzatib berishni, to'siq qo'yishda boshqa sheriklariga xalaqit qilmagan holda sakrashni aniq bajarishi kerak. Yosh voleybolchilarda sakrovchanlikni oshirishda maktabdan tashqari va maktab sharoitlarida har hil harakatli va xalq o'yinlaridan foydalanish bilan ham sakrovchanlikni oshirish mumkin. Masalan; «Qarmoqcha», «Chexarda», «Bo'ri zovur ichida», «Quyonglar polozda», «Ariqdan sakrab o'tish», «Oqsoq qarg'a», «Xo'rozlar jangi», «Eshak mindi», «Chivinni tut», «Quyonglar» va xokazo.

Sakrovchanlik va sakrash chidamkorligi o'yin mobaynida zarur rol o'ynabgina qolmay usullarini chaqqonlik bilan bajarish va o'yin davomida voleybolchini joy o'zgartirishi rivojlanishni yaqindan ta'minlaydi. O'yin ketayotgan bir jarayonda favqulotda har xil harakatga soluvchi vaziyatlar bo'lib qoladiki, bu vaziyatlar o'yinchini to'siq qo'yishda va zarba berishda tez va aniq fikrlashini talab qiladi.

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